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Eman (*Quercus Robur L*) po'stlog'ining kimyoviy tarkibi va tibbiyotda foydalanish o'rinlari

¹Atabekova Mashxura Usmanovna, ²Turdaliyev Ahrorbek Xoldarali o'g'li, ³Abduganiyev Xumoyun Abdulalim o'g'li

¹*Kokand university Andijon filiali, assistant*

²*Farmatsevtika mahsulotlari havfsizligi markazi» davlat muassasasining Andijon filiali Bosh mutaxasisi*

³*Andijon Davlat Tibbiyot Instituti 1-kurs Magisratura talabasi*

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Annotatsiya. Turli *Quercus* turlaridan olingan eman po'stlog'i o'zining bioaktiv tarkibiy qismlari, ayniqsa, taninlar, flavonoidlar va polifenollar bilan keng o'rganilgan. Ushbu tadqiqot eman po'stlog'ining kimyoviy tarkibini, an'anaviy va sanoat qo'llanilishi hamda samarali ekstraksiya usullarini tahlil qilishga qaratilgan. Adabiyotlar tahlili va eksperimental tekshiruvlar orqali asosiy bioaktiv moddalar va ularning mumkin bo'lgan qo'llanilishi muhokama qilinadi. Faol komponentlarni ajratib olishda samaradorligi baholangan turli ekstraksiya usullari, jumladan, suvli, etanol ekstraksiyasi ko'rib chiqiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: taninlar, flavonoidlar, bioaktiv moddalar, ekstraksiya usullari, Atom adsorbsion spektroskopiyasi, Yuqori samarali suyuqlik xromatografiyasi.

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Kirish. Eman po'stlog'i asrlar davomida an'anaviy tibbiyot, charm ishlab chiqarish va bo'yoq sanoatida keng qo'llanib kelgan. Uning polifenollar bilan boyligi antibakterial, yallig'lanishga qarshi va antioksidant xususiyatlarini tasdiqlaydi. Ushbu tadqiqot eman po'stlog'ining kimyoviy tarkibini o'rganish, uning sanoatdagi qo'llanilishi va bioaktiv moddalarning maksimal ajratilishi uchun samarali ekstraksiya texnikalarini baholashga qaratilgan.

Xalq tabobatida eman po'stlog'ining qaynatmasi diareya, dizenteriya, gastrit, o'pka tuberkulyozi va oshqozon-ichakdan qon ketishida (yara, gemorroyoid) gemostatik vosita sifatida ishlatiladi. Qaynatma, shuningdek, og'iz bo'shlig'i shilliq qavatining yallig'lanish kasalliklarida (stomatit, gingivit) og'izni yuvish uchun ishlatiladi. Zamonaviy tibbiyotda eman po'stlog'ining qaynatmasi og'iz tomog'ini chayish va chayishda (stomatit, gingivitda) biriktiruvchi va antiseptik sifatida

ishlatiladi. Bundan tashqari, u tish go'shtining qon ketishi va yomon nafas uchun chayish sifatida ishlatiladi. Eman po'stlog'i biriktiruvchi va antiseptik sifatida chayish uchun ishlatiladigan choy va infuziyalarga kiradi. Eman mevalaridan Ibn Sino gemoptizi, qonli diareya, ichakdan qon ketishda gemostatik vosita, shuningdek siydik haydovchi vosita sifatida foydalangan.

Metodologiya. Tadqiqot uchun *Quercus robur* (oddiy eman) daraxtlarining po'stlog'i namunalar sifatida tanlandi. Namunalar daraxtlarning sog'lom va zararkunandalardan himoyalangan qismidan olib, toza sharoitda saqlangan. Yig'ib olingan po'stloq tabiiy sharoitda, bevosita quyosh nurlari ta'sirisiz havo bilan quritildi. Quritish jarayoni to'liq tugagach, po'stloq mexanik maydalash usuli yordamida mayda kukunga aylantirildi. Tayyorlangan kukun kimyoviy tahlillar va ekstraksiya jarayonlari uchun maxsus yopiq idishlarda saqlanib, tashqi namlik va ifloslanishdan himoyalandi.

Eksperimental qism. Namunalarning kimyoviy tarkibini o'rganish maqsadida quyidagi tahlil usullari qo'llanildi: 1) Tanin miqdorini aniqlash: Tanin birikmalarining miqdori titrlash usuli yordamida aniqlandi. Buning uchun namunalar standart eritma bilan titrlanib, hosil bo'lgan rang o'zgarishi va hosil bo'ladigan kompleks birikmalar orqali hisob-kitob qilindi.

Flavonoid va fenol birikmalar tarkibni tahlil qilish: Flavonoid va umumiy fenolik birikmalarining miqdori yuqori samarali suyuqlik xromatografiyasi (YSSX) usuli yordamida tahlil qilindi. Bu usul har bir komponentni aniqlash va ularning tarkibiy nisbatini baholash imkonini beradi. 2) Mineral tarkibni aniqlash: Namunalardagi mineral elementlarning miqdori atom adsorbsion spektroskopiyasi (AAS) orqali o'lchandi. Ushbu usul namunadagi har xil metallar va minerallarni yuqori aniqlikda aniqlashga imkon beradi.

Ekstraksiya usullari. Tadqiqot davomida eman po'stlog'idan bioaktiv birikmalarni ajratib olish uchun uch xil ekstraksiya usuli solishtirildi: Suvli ekstraksiya: Eman po'stlog'i kukuni distillangan suvda 1 soat davomida qaynatildi. Keyin esa eritma xona haroratida sovutilib, vakuum filtratsiya usuli yordamida filtrlab olindi.

Etanol ekstraksiya: Namunalar 70% etanol eritmasida 24 soat davomida ekstraksiya qilindi. Jarayon tugagach, eritma suyuq-faza ajratish usuli yordamida tozalandi va erituvchi vakuum bug'lantirish orqali chiqarib tashlandi. Har bir ekstraksiya usulida hosil bo'lgan ekstraktlar kimyoviy tarkibi bo'yicha tahlil qilinib, ularning biologik faolligi solishtirildi.

Miqdoriy tahlil. Taninlarni aniqlash (O'zbekiston Respublikasi Davlat farmakopeyasi). Taxminan 2,0 g (aniq og'irligi) ezilgan xom ashyo diametri 3 mm bo'lgan elakdan o'tkazib, 500 ml sig'imli konussimon kolbaga solinadi, qaynaguncha

qizdirilgan 250 ml suv bilan quyiladi va elektr pechda 30 daqiqa davomida yopiq holda qaynatiladi. Suyuqlik xona haroratiga qadar sovutiladi va xom ashyo zarralari kolbaga tushmasligi uchun 200-250 ml sig'imli konussimon kolbaga paxta momig'i orqali filtrlanadi. So'ngra 25 ml olingan ekstrakt 750 ml sig'imli boshqa konussimon kolbaga pipetlanadi, unga 500 ml suv va 25 ml indigosulfon kislota eritmasi qo'shiladi va doimiy aralastirib, kaliy permanganatning 0,02 mol/l eritmasi bilan oltin sariq rang hosil bo'lguncha titrlanadi.

Nazorat tajribasi parallel ravishda amalga oshiriladi. 1 ml 0,02 mol/l kaliy permanganat eritmasi 0,004157 g tanin ga to'g'ri keladi.

Mutlaqo quruq xom ashyo asosida taninlarning (X) miqdori foizda quyidagi formula bo'yicha hisoblanadi:

$$X = \frac{(V - V_0) \times 0,004157 \times 250 \times 100 \times 100}{m \times 25 \times (100 - W)}$$

V - titrlash ekstrakti uchun ishlatiladigan 0,02 mol/l kaliy permanganat eritmasining hajmi, ml;

V₀ - nazorat tajribasida titrlash uchun sarflangan 0,02 mol/l kaliy permanganat eritmasining hajmi, ml;

0,004157 - 1 ml 0,02 mol/l kaliy permanganat eritmasiga (tanin bo'yicha) to'g'ri keladigan taninlar miqdori, g; V_t - xom ashyoni quritish paytida massaning yo'qolishi, %da;

250 - ekstraktsiyaning umumiy hajmi, ml; 25 - titrlash uchun olingan ekstrakt hajmi, ml.

Natijalar va muhokama. Eman po'stlog'ining kimyoviy tahlili yuqori konsentratsiyadagi taninlar va flavonoidlarni aniqladi ;

1-jadval: Eman po'stlog'ining Kimyoviy Tarkibi (100 g quruq massa uchun)

Modda nomlari	Konsentratsiya (%)
Taninlar	30–40
Flavonoidlar	5–10
Fenolik kislotalar	2–5
Lignin	15–20
Efir moylari	<1
Minerallar	3–7

Yuqori Tanin miqdori eman po'stlog'ini charm ishlab chiqarish va bo'yoq sanoati uchun mos ekanligini tasdiqlaydi. Flavonoidlar va fenolik kislotalarning mavjudligi uni tibbiyot va kosmetika sanoatida qo'llash imkoniyatini oshiradi. Suvli ekstraksiya an'anaviy usul bo'lib qolayotgan bo'lsada, etanol ekstraksiya bioaktiv moddalarning samarali balansini ta'minlaydi.

Xulosa. Eman po'stlog'i yuqori miqdordagi Taninlar, flavonoidlar va fenolik kislotalarni o'z ichiga oladi, bu esa uni turli sohalarda qo'llashga imkon beradi. Turli ekstraksiya usullari hosildorlik va tarkibga ta'sir qiladi, bunda etanol ekstraksiya samaradorlik va xarajat nuqtayi nazaridan optimal usul sifatida tavsiya etiladi. Kelajakdagi tadqiqotlar ekstraksiya sharoitlarini optimallashtirish va aniq bioaktiv moddalarning tahliliga qaratilishi lozim.

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E-mail:

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